

Re-discovery of living specimens of *Heliacus (Gyriscus) jeffreysianus* (Tiberi, 1867) (Gastropoda: Architectonicidae)

Redescubrimiento de ejemplares vivos de *Heliacus (Gyriscus) jeffreysianus* (Tiberi, 1867) (Gastropoda: Architectonicidae)

Constantine MIFSUD* and Panayotis OVALIS**

Recibido el 17-VII-2007. Aceptado 9-X-2007

ABSTRACT

Heliacus (Gyriscus) jeffreysianus (Tiberi, 1867), a rare architectonicid species associated with *Corallium rubrum* (L., 1758), has been rediscovered alive off Crete, eastern Mediterranean.

RESUMEN

Heliacus (Gyriscus) jeffreysianus (Tiberi, 1867), una especie rara de architectonico asociado a *Corallium rubrum* (Linnaeus, 1758), ha sido redescubierta con ejemplares vivos, frente a la isla de Creta en el Mediterráneo oriental.

KEY WORDS: Mollusca, Gastropoda, Architectonicidae, *Heliacus jeffreysianus*, Crete.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Mollusca, Gastropoda, Architectonicidae, *Heliacus jeffreysianus*, Creta.

INTRODUCTION

Heliacus (Gyriscus) jeffreysianus was described by TIBERI (1867) from three specimens collected from a red coral substratum off Sardinia. He described the species a year after its discovery, as stated by COEN (1932).

SYSTEMATICS

Original description: *Cochlea turbinata, elato-conica, turrata, modice umbilicata, inteofulvescens; apex obtusiusculus, laevigatus, vertice intorto, subperforato, spiraliter involuto; anfr. 7 convexi, sutura profunda divisim transverse cingulati, cingulis confortis, alternatim majoribus (num. fere 15 totidemque*

minaribus in ultima anfractu; num. 6 in penultimo), eleganter granulosis, submoniliformibus; anfr. Ultimus rotundatus, subinflatus, basi paululum depressus; umbilicus mediocris, pervius, superne circulariter crenulatus; apert. Subcircularis, effusa, intus haud margaritacea, marginibus acutis, callo parietali junctis; margine columellari sinuato, reflexo, umbilici partem occultante. – Diam. Maj. 9, min. 8, alt 10? mill. – Operculum corneum, superne nucleo centrali depresso lamellaque erecto-crenulata multispiratum, inferne processu centrali styloformi paucispirato praeditum, limbo peripherico incrassatum. – Animal hucusque incognitum.

Hab. In fundis coralligenis maris Sardiniam meridionalem ambientis.

* 5, Triq ir-Rghajja, Rabat RBT 2486, Malta

** Agsilaou 37-39, Tzitzifites/Kallithea, 17674 Athens, Greece

Figure 1. *Heliacus (Gyriscus) jeffreysianus* (Tiberi, 1867), off Crete Island on *Corallium rubrum* (Linnaeus, 1758) in 120m. Size: 9x8 mm. Photo P. Ovalis.

Figura 1. *Heliacus (Gyriscus) jeffreysianus* (Tiberi, 1867), frente a la isla de Creta sobre *Corallium rubrum* (Linnaeus, 1758) en 120m. Size: 9x8 mm. Foto P. Ovalis.

Tiberi dedicated his species to the illustrious malacologist John Gwyn Jeffreys (1809-1885). Two of the specimens are presently in the Coen collection at The Hebrew University, (Department of Zoology) Jerusalem, Israel and the other specimen is in the Jeffreys collection at the Smithsonian Institution, Washington (USA) (MELONE AND TAVIANI 1984).

New material: Two live specimens of *Heliacus (Gyriscus) jeffreysianus* were recently recovered from a living colony of *Corallium rubrum* (Linnaeus, 1758) from off the island of Crete at a depth of 120 m. Figure 1 shows one of the two similar specimens, measuring h= 9 mm x w= 8 mm which is about the same size as those found by Tiberi. The specimens were hand picked from a coral colony by a professional scuba diver from Crete using specialized diving equipment. It is not known whether the molluscs were actually feeding on the coral polyps. However, the species seems to have a close connection with *C. rubrum*. Several species from the family Architectonicidae are known to be parasitic on corals (BIELER 1993). Judging from the two presently known records, the species has always been found with these red corals, and as it is well known, it was never found in any other Mediterranean habitat notwithstanding the large amount of research carried out in the last hundred years.

Since its original description, the species had never been found again until recently, when living specimens of *Heliacus jeffreysianus* were collected in the Adriatic Sea (STANIC AND SCHIAPARELLI, 2007). It is very curious, but not surprising, that both this and our discoveries were recorded at the same time and at distantly separated places. This is certainly due to the more recent interest being undertaken both by amateur and professional researchers in the depths of the red and white coral substratum of the Mediterranean Sea. The authors are also aware of other unrecorded species living in this part of the Mediterranean, and originally described from deep water in the Atlantic.

Otherwise, *Heliacus jeffreysianus* has only been cited in the literature in a few species lists and catalogues pertaining to the Mediterranean malacofauna and it was even thought to be extinct. Moreover, no fossil specimens of the species have ever come to light (MELONE AND TAVIANI 1984).

MONTEROSATO (1880) had commented about the species of Tiberi "Il *G. jeffreysianus*, è una delle nostre più rare gemme, la cui scoperta, come di tante altre rarità coralligene, si deve al Dr. Tiberi. Soltanto tre esemplari ne sono conosciuti sinora. *Beati possidentes!* Io voglio ammettere che nella mente di un naturalista il *Gyriscus* abbia più valore

Figure 2. Map of the Mediterranean showing the three locations cited for *H. jeffreysianus*. 1: Sardinia Island; 2: Adriatic Sea; 3: Crete Island.

Figura 2. Mapa del Mediterráneo mostrando las tres localidades citadas para *H. jeffreysianus*. 1: isla de Cerdeña; 2: mar Adriático; 3: isla de Creta.

del più grosso diamante della corona d'Inghilterra, ma francamente il prezzo al quale lo vende il Dr. Tiberi, per una conchiglia così piccola, sarà riguardato tanto dai naturalisti quanto dai mercanti come assai esagerato”

In translation: “The *G. jeffreysianus* is one of our most rare gems, its discovery, like many other coralligenous rarities, is owed to Dr. Tiberi. Only three specimens are known up to now. *Blessed are the possessors!* I must admit that in the minds of the naturalist the *Gyriscus* has more value than the largest diamond from the British crown, but frankly the price which Dr. Tiberi has asked, for such a small shell is regarded by naturalists and also by merchants as being exaggerated.”

H. jeffreysianus is one of the most beautiful species from the family Architectonicidae. Its sculpture of small-beaded spiral chords and its trochoid shape make it outstanding and very distinguished among the other species of the family in the Mediterranean. In fact, Tiberi (1867) created a genus for it, *Gyriscus*, which is nowadays a subgenus of *Heliacus*. A very similar Pacific species is *H. (Gyriscus) asteleformis* (Powell, 1965) from New Zealand.

COEN (1932) figured the operculum from one of the two specimens in his collection (also figured in MELONE AND TAVIANI, 1984). MELONE AND TAVIANI (1984) described and figured a syntype

from the Coen collection. They also figured the radula (as redrawn after MERRIL, 1970). Other descriptions and diagnoses of the genus and the species can also be found in COEN (1932), MELONE AND TAVIANI (1984) and in BIELER (1993).

CONCLUSIONS

This very long elapsed period of over 140 years for the re-discovery for *H. jeffreysianus* is in all probability due to its rarity and the very particularly restricted and difficult to sample habitat. Red coral was traditionally harvested by fishermen utilizing a particular gear called the Cross, which consists of two large beams tied together in the form of a cross and armed with dangling ropes and pieces of netting to enable the coral to entangle during dredging. This heavy equipment, although it seemed adequate for the purpose, besides being very destructive to the substratum, constantly shakes the entangled corals and the molluscs seem to always fall off before the gear is brought aboard the vessel. The modern method of manual harvesting through SCUBA is more selective, and therefore much less destructive. However, it is much more risky and dangerous.

Curiously, this species had not been discovered on red coral before, although

the method of manual harvesting of coral by specialized deep diving equipment (using a mixture of gases) has now been in practice for many years, especially by Spanish, Italian and Greek coral divers. More probably, it may take the keen eyes of a biologist, a naturalist or a shell collector to notice and pick out the small mollusc shells in situ. Therefore any specimens brought up by chance by the fishermen or the divers are probably either thrown back into the sea with the other rubbish as in the case of the fishermen or in the case of the diver, they fall off the coral unnoticed during the long decompression process. Moreover, the diver would be even more concerned for his "treasure" rather than a few "worthless" shells. Although Mediterranean *Corallium rubrum* is also found at great depths in the Mediterranean, the two existing records of *H. jeffreysianus* are both from shallow

water living colonies. STANIC AND SCHIAPARELLI (2007) did not mention the species on which they found their specimens. Finally, this record extends the species distribution to quite a larger area of the Mediterranean (Fig. 2) and it is expected that more specimens which could contribute to the study of the biology of the species are likely to turn up.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank Agios Nicolaos, a specialized deep sea coral diver for donating one of the two specimens which he collected to one of the authors (P. O.) for this study. Thanks are also due to Sophie Valtat (Belgium) for providing important literature and to S. Gofas (Spain) for revising and enhancing the manuscript.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- BIELER, R., 1993. *Architectonicidae of the Indo-Pacific*. Gustav Fischer Verlag, pp. 377. Stuttgart.
- COEN, G. S., 1932. Sul genere *Gyriscus*, Tiberi, 1867. *Bollettino della Società Veneziana di Scienze Naturali*, 1 (1): 9-13.
- MELONE, G. AND TAVIANI, M., 1984. Revisione delle Architectonicidae del Mediterraneo. *Atti del Simposio: Sistematica dei Prosobranchi del Mediterraneo, Bologna 24-26 Settembre 1992*, (B. Sabelli, ed.) *Lavori S.I.M.*, 21: 149-192.
- MERRILL, A. S., 1970. *The family Architectonicidae (Gastropoda: Mollusca) in the western and eastern Atlantic*. Unpubl. Ph.D. Thesis, Univ. Delaware (Univ. Microfilms Int. Inc., Ann Arbor, Michigan, U.S.A., Nr. 7144444).
- MONTEROSATO, T. A., 1880. Nota sopra alcune conchiglie coralligene del Mediterraneo. *Bollettino della Società Malacologica Italiana*, 6: 243-259.
- STANIC, R. AND SCHIAPARELLI, S., 2007. New finding of living specimens of the rare architectonicid *Helicacis (Gyriscus) jeffreysianus* (Tiberi, 1867). *Bollettino Malacologico*, 43 (9-12): 143-146.
- TIBERI, N., 1867. Diagnose du nouveau genre méditerranéen *Gyriscus*. *Journal de Conchyliologie*, 15: 303. Paris.